

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR IMPROVING THE READINESS OF STUDENTS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY ON THE BASE OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

¹Khimmataliev Dustnazar Omonovich, ²Abdieva Ezoza, ³Tilovberdiev Shokhruh

¹Doctor of pedagogic sciences, professor

^{2,3}Students of the "School Management" course

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8345221>

Abstract. *Integrative approach is one of the important innovative phenomena in education. In the article, based on an integrative approach, the issues of improving students' readiness for professional activity, directions for improving readiness for professional activity, and the functions of professional training activities are highlighted.*

Keywords: *quality, education, modernization, concept, technology, manual, profession, experience, skill.*

The integrative approach in the pedagogical process is becoming one of the important components of the educational activity of the higher education institution. Because the integrative approach not only creates a basis for the competitiveness of one or another educational institution in the market of educational services, but also intensive development of the personality of the professor-teacher and student in the conditions of modernization of higher education, democratization of the joint activity and communication of professor-teachers and requirements in the conditions of modernization of higher education, the educational process performs tasks such as humanization, directing the student to receive active education and form himself in all aspects, improving and modernizing the technologies, methods and tools used in the educational process, strengthening the material and technical base of education.

A modern specialist should be distinguished by the fact that he is knowledgeable, ethical, active, responsible, capable of cooperation, creative, and uses an integrative approach to work. Integrative approach is one of the important innovative phenomena in education. Z.Sh.Karimov states: "It "exceeds all other phenomena" in terms of breadth of experimental implementation, depth of creative intention, continuity and dialectics of historical development [1].

Scientists interpret the integrative approach in pedagogy in different ways. I.A.Zimnyaya, E.V.Zemtsova define the integrative approach as "an integrated image of a set of objects, events, processes united by the commonality of at least one feature, as a result of which it has a new quality" [2].

The integrative approach is a creative and inquisitive approach aimed at creating a comfortable educational environment in accordance with the wishes and needs of the future teacher to ensure the integrity of the students' specialized knowledge, skills, practical methods of work and personal quality and qualities, as well as the goals and tasks of providing them with education. is a research activity [3].

The integrative approach includes any components of the pedagogical process, any events and subjects: material and ideal objects (concepts, principles, ideas, concepts, theories); activity

(methods, methods, skills, competencies, technologies); person (states, qualities, characteristics, motives) can be.

Based on the integrative approach, the following pedagogical conditions can be specified in order to improve students' readiness for professional activity:

- elimination of multiple subjectivity;
- reducing the time of studying a subject (section, entire course);
- elimination of repetitions;
- change of educational technology;
- creating relatively favorable conditions for the development of the learner;
- to encourage the acceleration of the development of learners and pedagogues.

On the basis of an integrative approach, it is necessary to know the ways of improving students' readiness for professional activity and to take into account the real needs of learners and pedagogues when organizing the pedagogical process. These needs, in turn, arise from the contradictions identified by the participants of the pedagogical process during the acquisition and delivery of the educational material.

The preparation of students for professional activity is determined by professional competence, including mastering, in-depth knowledge of the subject, and the ability to interest students.

Recently, expressions such as quality of life, quality of education, and social success are heard more and more. Improving the quality of education is the main task announced by the concept of modernization of education. Of course, this cannot be achieved without the introduction of innovative technologies, modern teaching aids, without increasing the prestige of the teaching profession, without identifying and disseminating advanced pedagogical experience. Because this cannot be achieved without improving the professional skills of each teacher.

Quality of education is a multifaceted concept. It is recommended to approach its disclosure in terms of the process approach adopted in the development of a quality management system to increase customer satisfaction by fulfilling their requirements. The preparation of students for professional activity is primarily determined by the quality of the knowledge carrier, who transmits this knowledge to students using various methods. Therefore, preparation for professional activity should begin with the formation of the pedagogical corps and the creation of conditions for its effective functioning. New textbooks, new pedagogical technologies are just weapons in the hands of the teacher. How effective this set of tools is depends on the level of preparation of the teacher. Based on the integrative approach, it is a mistake to think that the pedagogical conditions for improving students' readiness for professional activity can be implemented only through material incentives, i.e., salary increases, various allowances and awards. Of course, material incentives play an important role, but at the same time, low methods of moral incentives can play the role of a motivator to a greater extent than salary.

Based on the integrative approach, the pedagogical conditions for improving students' readiness for professional activity will change from the outside. In addition, on the basis of an integrative approach, the criteria for evaluating the readiness of students for professional activities can be determined through the functions of professional activities as follows:

- teaching (awakening motivation for professional activity);
- education (the content and essence of understanding one's suitability to the requirements of the chosen profession);

- methodism (self-improvement in professional activity and clear orientation to the profession);

- conducting experiments on the basis of such functions as research (reviewing the news in one's profession and working on oneself) and evaluating the results on the basis of motivational, cognitive, professional-activity criteria [4].

These performance functions include the following performance outcomes:

- taking into account the level of pedagogical-psychological knowledge, ability, attitude to events happening in the world and in our country;

- improvement of professional training of students on the basis of modern information and communication technologies, innovative technologies and foreign experiences, scientific ideas, integrative approach and its implementation based on the nature of the studied profession.

REFERENCES

1. Каримов З.Ш. Теория и практика институциональной интеграции высшего профессионального педагогического образования на основе синтеза внешнего и внутреннего компонентов: автореф. дис. ... д-ра пед. наук. – Уфа, 2009. – 48 с.
2. Зимняя И.А., Земцова Е.В. Интегративный подход к оценке единой социально-профессиональной компетентности выпускников вузов /И.А. Зимняя, Е.В. Земцова // Высшее образование сегодня. – 2008. – № 5. – С. 14–19.
3. Akhmedova N.M. The use of information and communication technologies in the continuous education system is the future of a mature generation. A collection of articles by talented students and young scientists. - T.:2015, pp. 120-123.
4. Akhmedova N.M. Doctor of Philosophy (PHD) dissertation on the topic of improving the professional training of future teachers based on an integrative approach. - Tashkent, TDPU, 2020.